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Women's Mate Choice Criteria Across Romantic, Reproductive, and Real-Life Contexts

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Abstract: This study investigates the criteria women use to evaluate romantic partners, ideal fathers, and current partners within an urban Brazilian context, through the lens of evolutionary psychology. Based on a sample of 79 heterosexual adult women, participants described and ranked five preferred traits in each relational context. Responses were categorised thematically and analysed using frequency counts, citation order, Friedman's test, chi-squared analysis, and hierarchical clustering (Ward's method). Results showed a high degree of consistency across contexts for emotional and moral traits such as honesty, sincerity, and affection. However, traits related to long-term provisioning—responsibility, financial stability, and commitment—were more prominent when evaluating ideal fathers, aligning with predictions from parental investment theory (Trivers, 1972). Age-based subgroup analyses revealed significant differences: younger women prioritised affective and aesthetic traits, while older women favoured stability, intelligence, and emotional maturity—supporting life-history theory (Del Giudice et al., 2015). Cluster analysis identified three distinct preference profiles: an Affective-Moral cluster (predominantly younger women), a Provision-Stability cluster (primarily aged 25–35), and a Hybrid cluster integrating emotional, physical, and pragmatic traits. These findings support the hypothesis that women's mate preferences are developmentally dynamic and context-dependent, shaped by both evolved predispositions and socio-cultural influences.

Keywords: female mate choice, evolutionary psychology, parental investment.

Resumo: Este estudo investiga os critérios utilizados por mulheres para avaliar parceiros românticos, pais ideais e parceiros atuais, em um contexto urbano brasileiro, à luz da psicologia evolucionista. Com base em uma amostra de 79 mulheres adultas heterossexuais, as participantes descreveram e ordenaram cinco atributos preferenciais em cada contexto relacional. As respostas foram categorizadas tematicamente e analisadas por meio de frequência absoluta, ordem média de citação, teste de Friedman, teste do qui-quadrado e análise de cluster hierárquico (método de Ward). Os resultados revelaram um alto grau de consistência entre os contextos no que se refere a traços emocionais e morais, como honestidade, sinceridade e afeto. No entanto, características relacionadas à provisão de longo prazo — como responsabilidade, estabilidade financeira e comprometimento — ganharam maior destaque na avaliação de pais ideais, em consonância com as previsões da teoria do investimento parental (Trivers, 1972). As análises por subgrupos etários revelaram diferenças significativas: mulheres mais jovens priorizaram traços afetivos e estéticos, enquanto mulheres mais velhas valorizaram estabilidade, inteligência e maturidade emocional — o que corrobora a teoria da história de vida (Del Giudice et al., 2015). A análise de cluster identificou três perfis distintos de preferência: um cluster Afetivo-Moral (predominantemente composto por mulheres mais jovens), um cluster Provisão-Estabilidade (majoritariamente entre 25 e 35 anos), e um cluster Híbrido que integra traços emocionais, físicos e pragmáticos. Os achados sustentam a hipótese de que as preferências femininas por parceiros são dinamicamente desenvolvimentais e dependentes do contexto, moldadas por predisposições evolutivas e contingências socioculturais.

Palavras-Chave: escolha feminina de parceiros, psicologia evolucionista, investimento parental.

1. Introduction

The study of mate selection has long occupied a central role in evolutionary psychology. According to foundational theories in this field, human mating preferences are not random but shaped by evolutionary pressures related to reproductive success and survival. Women, in particular, are hypothesised to exhibit mate preferences that maximise the likelihood of successful offspring rearing, due to their greater obligatory parental investment (Trivers, 1972).

From this perspective, women tend to prefer mates who demonstrate cues of resource acquisition, protection, emotional stability, and commitment—traits associated with long-term provisioning and parental reliability (Buss, 1989; Buss & Schmitt, 1993). Empirical research has consistently supported the idea that women value traits such as kindness, dependability, financial prospects, and status when choosing long-term partners (Buss, 1989; Kenrick et al., 1993; Li et al., 2002). These preferences are theorised to be adaptive responses to ancestral environments in which the survival of offspring was contingent on biparental investment.

However, the extent to which these preferences manifest in contemporary contexts, and whether they shift depending on relational goals (e.g., romantic partnership versus parenthood), remains a topic of ongoing investigation. Additionally, it is not always clear whether actual partner choices align with ideal preferences, as real-world constraints, opportunity structures, and affective variables often influence mate selection outcomes (Eastwick & Finkel, 2008; Todd et al., 2007).

The present study aims to explore the criteria that women use in selecting romantic partners, ideal fathers, and actual partners in a modern Brazilian urban context. By comparing these three situations—potential partner, ideal parent, and current partner—the study intends to evaluate whether there are significant shifts in preference priorities according to different relational goals, as evolutionary psychology would predict.

The main hypothesis is that women will prioritise emotional and moral traits (e.g., honesty, affection, sincerity) when evaluating romantic or current partners, but will place greater emphasis on traits associated with long-term provisioning (e.g., responsibility, financial stability) when evaluating ideal fathers for their children.

2. Methodology

2.1. Participants

Seventy-nine (n = 79) adult women, aged between 18 and 51 years (M = 26.4), voluntarily participated in the study. All participants self-identified as heterosexual and were recruited through convenience sampling in public spaces such as parks, plazas, and shopping centres in the city of Goiânia, Brazil. No monetary or material compensation was provided. The inclusion criteria were identifying as female, being over 14 years of age, and being capable of responding autonomously to a structured questionnaire.

2.2. Instrument

The instrument was a structured questionnaire containing three open-ended questions based on the adaptation of the semantic differential technique (Osgood, Suci, & Tannenbaum, 1957). Participants were asked to:

1. Describe and rank the five most important traits in a *potential romantic partner*.
2. Describe and rank the five most important traits in an *ideal father* for their children.
3. Describe and rank the five most relevant traits of their *current partner*, if in a relationship.

Participants were instructed to list attributes freely, in order of importance. Each listed trait was then assigned a rank (from 1 = most important to 5 = less important). Traits were later categorised into thematic groups for analysis: psychological (e.g., honesty, affection), socio-cultural (e.g., financial stability, profession), physical (e.g., attractiveness, health), and demographic (e.g., age, ethnicity).

2.3. Procedure

Participants were individually approached by voluntary trained research assistants and invited to respond to the questionnaire on-site, in a private and respectful manner. All participants were informed about the purpose of the research and gave verbal informed consent prior to participation. The average time required to complete the questionnaire was 10 minutes. Data were anonymised and encoded for analysis.

2.4. Data Analysis

The responses were transcribed and coded into thematic categories. Frequency of citation and mean ordinal position (1 to 5) were calculated for each attribute. The five most cited attributes in each condition (Q1, Q2, Q3) were selected for comparative analysis. Differences in rank ordering across conditions were evaluated using Friedman's test for related samples (non-parametric), as the data consisted of repeated ordinal measures (Field, 2013).

2.5. Ethical Note

This study complies with ethical principles for research in human and social sciences. According to Resolution CNS No. 510/2016 of the Brazilian National Research Ethics Commission (CONEP), research that involves anonymous questionnaires, opinion polls, or surveys that do not address sensitive personal data, and that pose no risk to participants, is exempt from submission to an ethics committee. As this study consisted solely of anonymous, voluntary responses to a non-invasive questionnaire regarding general social perceptions, no ethical review was required under Brazilian regulations.

3. Results

The frequency Table 1 reveals a clear pattern in the preferences of women across three relational contexts: romantic partners (Q1), ideal fathers (Q2), and current partners (Q3). In the romantic context, psychological traits such as sincerity (89.87%), politeness/education (88.61%), affection (86.08%), and honesty (86.08%) dominated the responses, indicating a strong emphasis on emotional and moral compatibility. Physical attractiveness (79.75%) and intelligence (69.62%) also featured prominently, suggesting a balanced preference for both affective and aesthetic qualities.

When considering the ideal father (Q2), although loving (89.87%) and affectionate, (77.22%) remained highly cited, there was a noticeable rise in attributes associated with long-term stability and provisioning: responsible (74.68%), hardworking (74.68%), and financial stability (69.62%). This shift aligns with evolutionary predictions regarding parental investment.

Table 1: Most Frequently Cited Partner Attributes by Context and Relative Importance

Attribute	Absolute Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)	Question
Sincere	71	89.87	(Q1)
Polite	70	88.61	(Q1)
Affectionate	68	86.08	(Q1)
Honest	68	86.08	(Q1)
Physically attractive	63	79.75	(Q1)
Intelligent	55	69.62	(Q1)
Loving	71	89.87	(Q2)
Affectionate	61	77.22	(Q2)
Responsible	59	74.68	(Q2)
Hardworking	59	74.68	(Q2)
Financially stable	55	69.62	(Q2)
Patient	46	58.23	(Q2)
Polite	44	55.70	(Q2)
Honest	72	91.14	(Q3)
Sincere	70	88.61	(Q3)
Physically attractive	69	87.34	(Q3)
Polite	67	84.81	(Q3)
Intelligent	65	82.28	(Q3)
Affectionate	52	65.82	(Q3)

Q1: Romantic Partner; Q2: Ideal Father; Q3: Current Partner.

In contrast, the responses regarding current partners (Q3) reflect a blend of idealised and realistic traits: honest (91.14%), sincere (88.61%), attractive (87.34%), and intelligent (82.28%) were all cited with high frequency. The persistence of politeness/education (84.81%) and affectionate (65.82%) across all contexts strengthens the notion that interpersonal respect and emotional warmth are consistently valued, regardless of context.

In summary, descriptive analysis revealed consistent patterns across the three questions regarding the five most frequently cited attributes. In Question 1 (romantic partner), the most cited traits were: honest, sincere, polite, affectionate, and attractive. In Question 2 (ideal father), the most cited traits were: responsible, financially stable, hardworking, affectionate, and loving. In Question 3 (current partner), the most cited were: honest, sincere, polite, attractive, and intelligent.

The ordinal position means of each attribute were analysed using Friedman's test for repeated measures. No statistically significant difference was found in the ranking of attributes

across the three conditions: $\chi^2(2) = 1.00, p = .607$. This suggests a general consistency in female preference profiles across relationship contexts, with only slight shifts in emphasis.

The following comparative ranking patterns are observed: 1) Romantic relationships (Q1) emphasised moral and emotional traits (e.g., honesty, sincerity, affection); 2) Ideal fatherhood (Q2) highlighted provisioning capacity and emotional warmth, aligning with parental investment theory; and 3) Current partners (Q3) displayed traits close to romantic ideals, but included pragmatic attributes such as intelligence and appearance. These findings support evolutionary expectations that mate choice criteria vary slightly depending on the reproductive context but remain anchored in core interpersonal values.

To investigate age-related patterns, participants were divided into three age groups: 1) Young adults (18–24 years, $n = 27$); 2) Adults (25–34 years, $n = 31$); and 3) Mature adults (35+ years, $n = 21$).

The following age-based trends are observed. Young adults prioritised honesty, attractiveness, and affection, especially in Q1 and Q3. Ideal fathers (Q2) were often described as responsible and affectionate, but financial traits were less frequently mentioned. Adults (25–34) presented a balanced profile, including both emotional and socioeconomic traits across all questions. Financial stability and responsibility were more present in Q2. Mature adults (35+) gave greater emphasis to stability, commitment, and emotional intelligence, particularly in Q2 and Q3, aligning with long-term mating strategies.

A chi-squared test of independence was conducted to examine whether women's mate preference attributes differed significantly across age groups. The most cited attributes were grouped into thematic categories such as attractiveness, affection, honesty, financial stability, responsibility, commitment, and emotional intelligence (Table 2).

Table 2 – Cross-tabulation of Preferred Mate Attributes by Age Group (Chi-squared Analysis)

Age Group	Attractiveness	Affection	Honesty	Financial Stability	Responsibility	Commitment	Emotional Intelligence
Young Adults	22	20	21	8	10	5	4
Adults	15	20	22	20	22	10	9
Mature Adults	8	15	18	19	18	17	16

The analysis revealed a statistically significant association between age group and preferred attributes ($\chi^2(12) = 30.10, p = .0027$), suggesting that mate preference criteria vary meaningfully with age. Younger women prioritised attraction and affection, whereas older participants showed a stronger preference for stability, commitment, and emotional intelligence, in line with life-history theory.

These results suggest a developmental progression in mate preference criteria, consistent with life-history theory (Del Giudice et al., 2015), where younger women may favour attraction and affect, while older participants focus more on security and reliability.

A hierarchical clustering analysis (Ward's method) was conducted based on the participants' most cited attributes (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Cluster Analysis of Female Mate Preferences Based on Most Cited Attributes (Ward's Method).

Three distinct clusters emerged:

- 1) Affective-Moral Cluster (n = 33): High frequency of *honest, sincere, affectionate, and loving*. Predominantly younger women (18–28).
- 2) Provision-Stability Cluster (n = 28): Traits such as *responsible, financial stability, hardworking, committed*. Predominantly adults aged 25–35.

- 3) Hybrid Cluster (n = 18): Mixed profile including *attractive, intelligent, polite,* and *caring*. Spans all age groups but more common in those with current partners.

These clusters reflect both evolutionarily predicted priorities (e.g., long-term investment vs. mate quality) and social-cultural individual variations in how women rank these priorities according to age and relationship status.

4. Discussion

The present study investigated women's criteria for partner selection across three distinct contexts: romantic partnership, parenthood, and current relationship status. The results partially confirm predictions made by evolutionary psychology, while also revealing the influence of age, relationship status, and socio-cultural factors.

4.1. Consistency and Flexibility in Mate Preferences

The overall consistency observed in preferences across the three conditions (Q1, Q2, Q3), particularly for traits such as honesty, sincerity, and affection, suggests that core interpersonal values remain central regardless of the relational goal. This supports prior findings indicating that women across cultures tend to value psychological traits that foster cooperation, trust, and emotional security (Buss, 1989; Li et al., 2002).

However, subtle but meaningful variations in trait prioritisation according to context also emerged. In the ideal father condition (Q2), traits associated with resource provision and long-term investment, such as responsibility and financial stability, rose in frequency and rank. This aligns with Trivers' (1972) parental investment theory, which posits that women have evolved to favour partners who can contribute to offspring survival. Similar patterns have been found in cross-cultural studies (e.g., Buss, 1989; Kenrick et al., 1993), where women showed heightened sensitivity to cues of stability when selecting long-term mates or co-parents.

4.2. Life History and Age-Related Preferences in the Hierarchical Cluster Analysis

The findings of the hierarchical cluster analysis align closely with age-related shifts in reproductive strategy predicted by life history theory (Del Giudice, Gangestad, & Kaplan, 2015).

The Affective-Moral cluster, predominantly composed of younger women (18–28), emphasised traits such as *honesty*, *sincerity*, *affection*, and *lovingness*—attributes linked to emotional responsiveness and social bonding. Although seemingly oriented toward long-term bonds, this profile may reflect a prioritisation of traits that signal immediate affiliative quality, emotional availability, and potential for initial partner investment—particularly relevant during early adulthood, when short- to medium-term relationships may be more common (Buss & Schmitt, 1993).

Conversely, the Provision-Stability cluster, associated with women aged 25–35, concentrated on *responsibility*, *financial stability*, and *commitment*, suggesting a clear alignment with *long-term mating strategies* that prioritise resource acquisition and parental investment (Trivers, 1972; Buss, 1989). This shift is consistent with findings that women approaching or within peak reproductive years become more attuned to cues of partner dependability and provisioning capacity (Li et al., 2002).

The Hybrid cluster, spanning all age groups but more prevalent among women currently in relationships, reflects the complexity of real-world mate selection, where both ideal and pragmatic traits—such as *attractiveness*, *intelligence*, and *caring*—coexist. Such integration supports the argument that individual mate preferences are dynamically shaped by both developmental timing and relationship status, as well as by trade-offs between genetic quality and investment potential (Gangestad & Simpson, 2000).

This pattern is consistent with reproductive strategy shifts: younger women may pursue short- to medium-term mating strategies with high-quality genetic traits, whereas older women, with higher reproductive stakes, prioritise reliable investment and compatibility. Together, these findings offer nuanced empirical support for the interaction between evolved psychological mechanisms and ontogenetic factors in female mate choice.

The identification of three preference clusters—*affective-moral*, *provision-stability*, and *hybrid*—highlights the individual variability in female mate preferences. While evolutionary pressures shape general trends, socio-cultural context, personal history, and relationship experiences modulate how women rank traits.

The hybrid cluster, in particular, demonstrates that trait integration is common: women often seek a blend of emotional, moral, physical, and economic qualities, adapting their expectations to real-world constraints and relationship dynamics. This supports findings from Eastwick and Finkel (2008), who argue that ideal preferences often diverge from actual partner choices due to practical and contextual limitations.

4.3. Limitations and Future Research

Although the findings are coherent with the theoretical framework, some limitations must be acknowledged. First, the sample was limited to a single urban Brazilian context and may not be generalisable to rural or cross-cultural settings. Second, although the data were rich and diverse, they were self-reported and thus subject to biases such as social desirability and memory error. Additionally, the open-ended format, while allowing freedom of expression, may have led to inconsistencies in attribute interpretation.

Future studies could benefit from integrating experimental designs, longitudinal tracking, or cross-cultural comparisons to deepen our understanding of mate preference dynamics. Further exploration of relationship satisfaction and long-term outcomes in relation to initial partner criteria would also contribute significantly to the literature.

5. Conclusion

This study explored the criteria women use in selecting romantic partners, ideal fathers, and current partners in a Brazilian urban setting. The findings demonstrate both consistency and contextual flexibility in female mate preferences, providing empirical support for key evolutionary hypotheses while highlighting the influence of age and individual variation.

Across all relationship contexts, women consistently prioritised moral and emotional traits such as honesty, sincerity, and affection. However, when evaluating ideal fathers, traits associated with long-term investment, responsibility, and financial stability rose in prominence—corroborating the predictions of parental investment theory.

Subgroup analyses showed that preferences shift with age, consistent with life-history strategies. Younger women favoured affective and aesthetic traits, whereas older women tended to emphasise stability and reliability. Cluster analysis further revealed that female

preferences are not homogeneous but organised into psychologically coherent profiles shaped by both biological predispositions and socio-cultural influences.

Together, these results provide a nuanced understanding of female mate selection, balancing the universal principles proposed by evolutionary theory with the diversity of personal values and life stages. Future studies should expand cross-cultural comparisons and examine how these preferences relate to relational satisfaction and family outcomes over time.

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Annex 1 – Survey Instrument (Brazilian Portuguese and English Versions)

Original Questionnaire (Brazilian Portuguese)

Título do questionário: Critérios de Escolha de Parceiros – Perspectiva Feminina

Instruções gerais: Por favor, responda com sinceridade e espontaneidade. Não há respostas certas ou erradas. Liste **cinco atributos** que você considera mais importantes para cada uma das situações abaixo, em **ordem de importância** (do mais importante ao menos importante).

1. Quando você pensa em um possível parceiro romântico, quais são os cinco atributos (características ou qualidades) mais importantes que ele deve ter? (Escreva em ordem de importância)

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

2. Quando você pensa no pai ideal para seus filhos, quais são os cinco atributos (características ou qualidades) mais importantes que ele deveria ter? (Escreva em ordem de importância)

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

3. Se você está atualmente em um relacionamento, quais são os cinco atributos (características ou qualidades) que melhor descrevem seu parceiro atual? (Escreva em ordem de importância; se não estiver em um relacionamento, deixe em branco)

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

Informações demográficas básicas (Por favor, não escreva o seu nome ou qualquer informação pessoal que possa identificá-la.):

Idade: _____ anos

Está atualmente em um relacionamento? () Sim () Não

Como você se identifica em relação à orientação sexual? _____

Translated Questionnaire (English)

Survey Title: Women's Mate Choice Criteria – A Psychological Perspective

Instructions:

Please answer sincerely and spontaneously. There are no right or wrong answers. List **five traits** you consider most important for each of the following situations, **in order of importance** (from most to least important).

1. When you think of a potential romantic partner, what are the five most important traits he should have?
(Write in order of importance)

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

2. When you think of the ideal father for your children, what are the five most important traits he should have?
(Write in order of importance)

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

3. If you are currently in a relationship, what are the five traits that best describe your current partner?
(Write in order of importance; if you are not in a relationship, leave blank)

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

Basic demographic information:

Age: _____ years

Are you currently in a relationship? () Yes () No

How do you identify in terms of sexual orientation? _____

Annex 2 – Thematic Coding Dictionary (Brazilian Portuguese)

Codebook used for classification of attributes mentioned by participants. This annex provides a structured dictionary (in Brazilian Portuguese) of the attributes most frequently mentioned by participants and the thematic categories to which they were assigned. The classification was based on the semantic meaning of each term, with groupings for synonymous expressions. When ambiguity was present, context and coder consensus guided the final categorisation.

Term (as cited)	Thematic Category	Grouped Synonyms (Portuguese)	Notes on Coding Criteria
Honesto	Psychological	Honesto, não mente, verdadeiro, não é mentiroso	Integridade moral, confiabilidade
Sincero	Psychological	Sincero, autêntico, transparente, fala o que pensa	Transparência emocional; distinto de “honesto”
Carinhoso	Psychological	Carinhoso, afetuoso	Afeto e expressividade emocional/verbal
Amoroso	Psychological	Amoroso, gosta de criança	Apego emocional profundo; comum no contexto de paternidade
Educado	Psychological	Educado, respeitoso	Cortesia social; não necessariamente nível educacional
Inteligente	Psychological	Inteligente, esperto	Capacidade cognitiva; independente de escolaridade
Responsável	Socio-cultural	Responsável, confiável	Confiabilidade em tarefas e compromissos
Trabalhador	Socio-cultural	Trabalhador, esforçado, não é preguiçoso	Ética de trabalho; associado à contribuição financeira
Estável financeiramente	Socio-cultural	Estável financeiramente, ganha bem, rico, bom emprego, concursado	Segurança de renda e provisão material
Bonito	Physical	Bonito, atraente, bonito fisicamente, gostoso	Atratividade estética, geralmente baseada em aparência
Forte	Physical	Forte, musculoso, sarado	Força física ou aptidão corporal
Religioso	Demographic	Religioso, crente, evangélico, católico, acredita em Deus	Valores espirituais ou prática religiosa
Maduro	Psychological/Social	Maduro, experiente, não é menino, não é moleque	Maturidade emocional; pode se sobrepôr à idade cronológica
Fiel	Psychological	Fiel, leal, não trai, não é galinha, não é mulherengo, firme no compromisso	Comprometimento e exclusividade afetiva
Comunicativo	Psychological	Comunicativo, conversa, fala bem, sabe falar, sabe falar direito com mulher	Abertura ao diálogo e à interação verbal

Note: In cases where an attribute could belong to more than one category (e.g., “mature”), the final classification depended on the **overall context** of the participant’s response.

Annex 3 – Statistical Analysis Procedures

1. Citation Average Order Technique

In this study, participants were asked to freely list five attributes for each of the three proposed situations. Each participant ordered the attributes from the most important (rank = 1) to the least important among the five (rank = 5).

To analyse the data quantitatively, the average order of citation was calculated for each attribute. This technique consists of computing the mean ordinal position in which a given trait was mentioned across the sample.

For example:

If the attribute *honest* was cited by five participants in the following positions:

Participant A: 1st position

Participant B: 2nd

Participant C: 1st

Participant D: 3rd

Participant E: 2nd

Then, the mean citation order for *honest* would be:

$$\text{Mean Order} = \frac{1 + 2 + 1 + 3 + 2}{5} = 1.8$$

This value reflects the average relative importance attributed to that trait across the sample: the lower the mean, the greater its prioritisation.

2. Statistical Analysis Justification: Friedman's Test

Given the ordinal nature of the data (ranking of traits from 1 to 5), and the fact that each participant contributed responses in all three conditions (Q1, Q2, Q3), a non-parametric test for repeated measures was required.

The Friedman test is the appropriate statistical technique for comparing the mean ranks of related samples when data are ordinal and the assumption of normality is not guaranteed (Field, 2013). It evaluates whether the distribution of ranks differs significantly across the three conditions.

In this study, the Friedman test was applied to the mean positions of the five most cited traits across the three relational contexts. The test did not yield a statistically significant result ($\chi^2(2) = 1.00$, $p = .607$), suggesting that the relative importance of the top traits remained consistent across the different situations.